

INFORMATION SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Annotation: *The article aims to create an information learning environment, to introduce a systematic approach to its management, to define the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution in accordance with the content of modern education at the initial stage of this approach. The purpose of modern education is to consist of a system of knowledge, skills and abilities formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, the purpose of the electronic information-educational environment in higher pedagogical education, to develop in direct connection with the requirements of the student issues that are important in shaping student personality have been interpreted.*

Key words: *education, student, information, supply, process, management, mastery, aspiration, impact, quality, result, formation.*

The current stage of education reform puts forward urgent tasks related to the speed of renewal in society, the rapid adaptation to new, higher requirements for educational institutions. In this context, the weight of measures aimed at developing the educational institution and ensuring that it operates at the level of modern requirements is constantly growing. Almost all of the tasks set are fundamentally new, and it is not enough for the team to work on the basis of existing experience alone. An analysis of research on the theory and practice of management of educational institutions shows that in modern conditions, the management of an educational institution remains directly related to the management of the exchange of information in it. This, in turn, shows that the improvement of the educational institution can be achieved through the effective use of information technology, and leads to the need for targeted research in this area.

The creation of an electronic information educational environment of the educational institution is not only a purely technical issue, but also requires the use of scientific, methodological, organizational and

pedagogical capabilities of the institution on the basis of a systematic approach [1].

In our opinion, the concept of "electronic information-educational environment" can be defined as a set of software, information-technical, educational-methodical systems that provide a goal-oriented learning process [2, 3]. Electronic information-educational environment is characterized by the following typological features:

1. The electronic information-educational environment at any level is a complex structural object of a systemic nature.

2. The integrity of the electronic information-educational environment is synonymous with the concept of achieving systemicity, combining them with the educational goals in the implementation of the personal and professional model of the graduate of the educational institution.

3. The electronic information-educational environment is not only a factor influencing the effectiveness of educational work, but also a tool.

Alternatively, there are a number of differing views on the definition of an information-learning environment, including:

- an organized set of information, technical, educational and methodological support, which is inextricably linked with the individual as a subject of the educational environment;

- a single information educational environment based on the integration of electronic information carriers, virtual libraries, distributed databases, computers, educational and methodological complexes, information and communication technologies [4].

A systematic approach to creating and managing an information learning environment is required. In the first stage of this approach, the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution is determined in accordance with the content of modern education [5]. In pedagogical activity, the purpose of education plays a systematic role. The clearly defined goal serves as a basis for choosing the content, purpose, organizational forms of education. The goal of modern education is a system of knowledge, skills and competencies that is formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, which is reflected in the relevant educational standards [13]. In addition, the student's personality is not only the object of the pedagogical process, but also its subject. In such cases, the importance of the student's independent learning increases and requires the formation of the following skills and competencies:

1. Skills and competencies for planning independent learning: developing an individual plan for independent activity; targeted activities based on a plan; monitor its activities and make necessary corrections.

2. Skills and abilities to use scientific and educational information on the Internet: independent identification of scientific and educational information; independent analysis and evaluation of new information; search and find sources of information on the Internet in terms of the problem to be solved; to be able to see new and promising news in the content of the received information.

3. Skills and abilities to work on electronic information and educational resources: systematic use of electronic manuals and catalogs; Be able to keep a list of scientific, educational and other literature obtained from the Internet in accordance with the rules of bibliography.

4. Skills and abilities to master the lectures presented by means of modern information technologies: to determine the topic and plan of lectures, the list of references; correct receipt of information provided; distinguish the main problem, idea and conclusion; write a summary of the main content in your own words; to process, store the information provided and use its content for educational purposes.

5. Skills and abilities to work with the electronic textbook: to get acquainted with the electronic textbook in general, to know its author, content, conclusion, illustrations and annotations; distinguish the logical structure of the electronic textbook; additional guides to fully understand the topic under study: animation, dictionary, encyclopedia, reference books; to record the received information in the form of abstracts, abstracts.

The e-learning environment has the following three main functions:

- to help the subjects of the external environment to form an idea of the information-educational environment of the educational institution with the help of modern information technologies;

- increase the interaction of the staff of the educational institution and create an environment for the exchange of information and educational resources;

- organization and management of effective information exchange in the educational institution through the means of information-educational environment [6, 7, 8, 9].

Defining the purpose of the information-educational environment in the educational institution is carried out taking into account the periodic sequence of three processes: in the first period the results of the analysis of the environment are studied; in the second period - the measures to be

taken accordingly are determined; in the third period the purpose of the information-educational environment of direct educational institution is developed [10, 11].

The purpose of the electronic information-educational environment in the higher pedagogical educational institution is developed in direct connection with the requirements to the future teacher [12]. In turn, in the formation of the personality of the future teacher, special attention is paid to the formation of qualities aimed at continuous self-development during post-graduate work. In this regard, it should be noted that the ongoing educational reforms in the country require a new interpretation of the concept of "profession". According to the requirements of the national model of training, a modern professional is characterized not only by a set of ready professional knowledge, but also by skills that contribute to professional development, the ability to analyze their professional level, readiness to acquire new knowledge in accordance with society and industry. The basis of the listed qualities is a developmental process aimed at the implementation of continuous professional training through the acquisition of new knowledge throughout life.

Thus, the organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes requires the study of the electronic information-educational environment of pedagogical education, the creation of integrated information-educational resources as a factor in improving the quality of education.

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